

M16 TANDEM transdisciplinary knowledge co-production framework

Periodic update 2: Tandem refined and iteratively applied

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Contents

Table of Figures	4
Index of Tables.....	5
List of Abbreviations	6
1 Background.....	7
1.1 The implementation of Tandem	7
1.1.1 RWL 1: Capital Region of Denmark	12
1.1.2 RWL 2: Emilia-Romagna Region	19
1.1.3 RWL 3: The Danube Region.....	28
1.1.4 RWL 4: Rhine-Erft	37
2. Refining Tandem	46
2.1 Methodology.....	46
2.1.1 Coding framework design	48
2.1.2 Coding framework implementation.....	51
3. Results.....	52
3.1 Phase of Co-exploration	52
3.1.1 Co-exploring challenges and goals	52
3.1.2 Tandem and co-exploring governance context	54
3.1.3 Tandem and co-exploration of information needs	55
4. Refining Tandem	56
4.1 Integration of DRR and CCA	56
4.2 Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach.....	57
4.3 Citizen engagement	57
4.4 Communicating uncertainty	58
4.5 Data interoperability	58
4.6 Capacity development.....	58
4.7 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning.....	59
References	60

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Tandem framework (Bharwani et al., 2024).....	11
Figure 2: Guide to coding in qualitative coding software (AtlasTi).....	50

Index of Tables

Table 1: WP 4-led RWL engagements and consultations.....	8
Table 2: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 1 context	13
Table 3: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 1:	14
Table 4: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information needs in RWL 1:.....	15
Table 5: RWL 1 document sources	19
Table 6: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 2 context:	20
Table 7: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 2:	22
Table 8: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 2 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem):	24
Table 9: RWL 2 document sources	28
Table 10: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 3 context	30
Table 11: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 3	32
Table 12: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 3 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem)	34
Table 13: RWL 3 document sources	37
Table 14: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 4 context	39
Table 15: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 4	41
Table 16: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 4 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem)	42
Table 17: RWL 4 document sources	45
Table 18: The combination of Tandem guiding questions categorized under sub-code themes, and the “good principles” of co-production, providing a categorisation scheme to evaluate successes and challenges of co-production in RWLs.	47

List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
WP	WORK PACKAGE

1 Background

WP 4 (led by SEI) will iteratively apply and refine the Tandem co-production framework (Daniels et al., 2020) in collaboration with WP 1 (Real Word Labs, RWLs) and within the wider Risk-Tandem process (WP 3) and as outlined in D1.2 (Capacity Development Strategy for the Training of Trainers). The refinement will be based on empirical evidence, lessons learned, emerging challenges and potential solutions. Collation and analysis of this evidence will be done between M6-48 to further refine Tandem into replicable, proven, and tested guidance for transdisciplinary co-production and information interoperability within disaster risk management (DRM) and climate change adaptation (CCA) contexts, leading to deliverable D4.3.

This milestone shows progress leading to D4.3 in M48 by: 1) explaining the qualitative coding methodology used to analyze the effectiveness of the co-production process; 2) sharing results of this analysis of qualitative data from interviews, consultations, workshops, surveys, and other engagements with RWLs to date; 3) reviewing gaps in the Tandem framework and how these can be addressed to refine and improve the guidance; and, 4) providing recommendations for the next periodic update to strengthen the Tandem cycle.

It is important to note that this report is distinct from the Knowledge co-production Outcomes reports, (WP 1, M3-M6). Whereas they seek to report on the progress made in terms of co-production outcomes from the perspective of the RWLs and their hosts, this milestone seeks to elaborate on the quality of the co-production process using the Tandem framework to support those outcomes. In other words, it provides an analysis of enablers contributing to successful co-production, and explains potential gaps in the current Tandem approach (Bharwani et al., 2024) to identify opportunities for further refinement and development.

1.1 The implementation of Tandem

During 2024, the Tandem guidance has been iteratively mainstreamed throughout RWL activities (as a part of the Risk-Tandem Phase II) to enable co-exploration in stakeholder workshops and between partners (Task 4.1). This has been informed by the combination of tailored 1-1 support consultations, the scoping for RWL needs, and formal capacity development (T4.2). **Here, it is also important to note that the knowledge co-production process itself contributes to capacity development, as a learning process for involved**

stakeholders. In practice, WP 4-led RWL engagements and consultations (Table 1) have aimed to identify opportunities for integrating transdisciplinary collaboration methods and Tandem guidance into workshop planning and design, and promote co-production between RWL stakeholders. This report seeks to link workshop outcomes and RWL progress to the Tandem framework, in efforts to explore the effectiveness of the co-production process in RWL contexts, but also to identify gaps for further refining the framework in risk governance contexts seeking to integrate DRR, CCA and enable multi-hazard management. WP 4 has also worked alongside WP 3, often sharing consultations to avoid contributing to stakeholder fatigue (and to align Tandem with the Risk-Tandem process, T3.2), and has contributed to the process of mapping user needs for the purposes of the Data Fabric (WP 5).

Table 1: WP 4-led RWL engagements and consultations.

Date	Type of engagement	Description	RWL	Lead WP
13/12/2023	Scoping	Scoping of needs	RWL 1	WP 4
14/12/2023	Scoping	Scoping of needs	RWL 3	WP 4
22/01/2024	Scoping	Scoping of needs	RWL 4	WP 4
23/01/2024	Scoping	Scoping of needs	RWL 2	WP 4
13/03/2024	Support	Simulation planning for GA in Rimini	RWL 2	WP 3/WP 4, all
26/03/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: webinar on citizen engagement	All	WP 4/WP 3
27/03/2024	Scoping	Workshop debrief	RWL 4	WP 4/WP 3
09/04/2024	Scoping	Scoping of needs	RWL 3 (Zala)	WP 4/WP 3
23/04/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: webinar on RiskPACC, citizen engagement and risk communication	All	WP 4/WP 3, all
24/04/2024	Support	Support and ideas for stakeholder interviews	RWL 1	WP 3/WP 4
26/04/2024	Support	Support and ideas for interviews and workshop planning	RWL 3	WP 3/WP 4
08/05/2024	Support	Support and planning of Rimini GA + simulation	RWL 2, all	All
09/05/2024	Support	Support and planning of Rimini GA + simulation	RWL 2, all	All

10/05/2024	Support	Support for workshop planning, reflection on interviews	RWL 3	All
14/05/2024	User needs	User needs discussions, data fabric	RWL 3	WP 5, WP 3, WP 4
16/05/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: monitoring, evaluation, and knowledge co-production	All	WP 4
21/05/2024	User needs	User needs discussions, data fabric	RWL 4	WP 5, WP 3, WP 4
21/05/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: webinar and ideas exchange – lessons from the civil protection of Service	All	WP 4
27/05/2024	User needs	User needs discussions, data fabric	RWL 3	WP 5, WP 3, WP 4
30/05/2024	Scoping	Debrief on stakeholder interview results	RWL 1	WP 3, WP 4
31/05/2024	Scoping	Scoping of needs and status	RWL 3	WP 4, WP 3
11/06/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change	RWL 1	WP 4, WP 3
25/06/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change	RWL 4	WP 4, WP 3
27/06/2024	Support	Support for workshop planning: draft agenda	RWL 1	WP 4, WP 3
28/06/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change	RWL 3	WP 4, WP 3
04/07/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: MEL and establishing a theory of change for	RWL 2	WP 4, WP 3
11/07/2024	Support	Support for workshop design and engagement	RWL 1	WP 3, WP 4
22/06/2024	Support	Support for workshop design and engagement	RWL 2	WP 3/WP 4
09/07/2024	Scoping	Scoping on wildfire risk management to support workshop	RWL 2	WP 4, WP 3
25/07/2024	Capacity development	Capacity development: introduction to gender, social equity and directed	All	WP 4
16/08/2024	Support	Support for workshop design	RWL 1	WP 3, WP 4

02/09/2024	Support	Modelling rehearsal for workshop	RWL 3	WP 5, all
12/09/2024	Scoping	Workshop debrief	RWL 1	WP 4, WP 3
19/09/2024	Scoping	Workshop debrief	RWL 4	WP 4, WP 3
07/10/2024	Scoping	Scoping: tailoring of Risk-Tandem and capacity development needs	RWL 2/RWL 4	WP 4, WP 3
11/10/2024	Scoping	Scoping: tailoring of Risk-Tandem and capacity development needs	RWL 1	WP 4, WP 3
14/10/2024	Scoping	Deep dive into theory of change: establishing a model case	RWL 4	WP 4
16/10/2024	Scoping	Scoping: tailoring of Risk-Tandem and capacity development needs	RWL 3	WP 4
18/10/2024	Scoping	Scoping: tailoring of Risk-Tandem and capacity development needs	RWL 3	WP 4

In each RWL case, these engagements have sought to enable the co-exploration of RWL risk governance contexts, through the active integration of Tandem guidance (Figure 1) and co-production activities (also between partners and RWL hosts). More thorough updates are provided under Milestones 3 and 4 (knowledge co-production outcomes reports) – only a brief overview is provided here to discuss the Tandem implementation.

Figure 1: Tandem framework (Bharwani et al., 2024).

[Tandem questions](#) under ‘Co-exploration’ (Phase II) have included guidance and considerations on i) co-exploring climate and risk-related challenges; ii) the governance context (including types, scales and levels of participation); and, iii) information needs (such as available data, models, information sources, and assumptions underpinning risk and climate data). It should be noted that WP 5 has led the discussion regarding user needs, and will thus provide learning for improving the ‘Co-design’ (Phase III) of the Tandem framework. Collaboration is gearing toward improving the use and communication of information from highly-technical toward accessible, to promote its uptake across RWL contexts.

1.1.1 RWL 1: Capital Region of Denmark

In early 2024, RWL 1 had minor delays relating to staff turnover and changing of dedicated hosts, and thus the team prioritized returning to regular momentum. Building upon initial scoping efforts and the 2023 workshop, engagement continued via bi-lateral discussions to ensure commitment and interest of stakeholders, and progressed to interviews in April and May 2024 to “set the stage” for the co-exploration workshop on 20 August 2024. WPs 3 and 4 provided their support to the interviews, contributing to the questionnaire to ensure critical DIRECTED interested areas were addressed, and that relevant Tandem questions pertaining to the phase of co-exploration were considered. RWL 1 hosts categorized questions according to the disaster management cycle (from preparedness and response to recovery and prevention), in efforts to identify gaps, needs and windows of opportunity regarding the governance context, data and information, to also benefit WPs 3 and 5 (regarding user needs and the Data Fabric).

Results of this interview were used to support the design of the August workshop, dedicated to co-exploring shared challenges and opportunities to develop integrated risk governance solutions (for strengthening emergency response, and supporting long-term planning via the integration of climate considerations to risk reduction planning). The workshop was planned from May to July (Table 1), in coordination with WPs 3, 4 and 5, as the agenda also included a demonstration of DIRECTED’s SaferPlaces and RIM2D models. Framed around a storm scenario “Bodil 2.0” (severe storm of the 2013), the modelling and associated discussions sought to unpick specific stakeholder needs, priorities and current challenges vis-à-vis the projected event, and prioritize issues identified in the interviews to generate a consensus. These supported the establishment of goals and priorities for the RWL, to support the co-production of technical and risk governance “solutions” during 2025-2026, guided by relevant Tandem (and Risk-Tandem) questions around the event scenario. Knowledge co-production methods and ideas were discussed between partners and hosts to promote interactivity and non-hierarchical collaboration between stakeholders. Alongside a prioritization exercise, the agenda also included a visioning exercise to co-explore and “define” a desired future state for risk governance by 2025, and outlined long-term as well as short-term needs that could be addressed during DIRECTED. These were introduced to promote the open sharing of perspectives and ideas, and to enable multi-sectoral thinking facing complex issues (including the compound/cascading effects of storm surges, wind, and rainfall in the Capital Region).

Table 2: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 1 context.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews and workshop
2.1 Co-exploring risk/adaptation challenges	2.1.1 What are the risk and adaptation challenges currently experienced, and what are their drivers (including physical, social, economic, or political dimensions)?	Partly addressed in interviews and the workshop. Some socio-economic and political drivers of challenges identified.
	2.1.3. What risk or adaptation challenges expressed by stakeholders could be addressed with better information?	Some information needs have been identified, especially in terms of compound flood events.
	2.1.4. Who is affected by risks and how? What characteristics contribute to their vulnerability and how? AND 2.1.7. What other drivers of change related to social vulnerability and socio-economic development exacerbate challenges?	Discussions regarding vulnerability are difficult to instigate – technical solutions preferred. Danish Coastal authority maintains a vulnerability index that could become useful as a component of the data fabric.
	2.1.5. What are the climate risks, sectors, and spatiotemporal scales for addressing risk governance challenges?	Identified scales range between short term needs for supporting emergency response to 2050 projections regarding future climate impacts on risks in the area.
	2.1.10/11/12 What are the existing climate services or warning systems that could be used to reduce risks, and how can they be made useful?	The DTU provides meteorological information to most stakeholders. Some gaps have been noted in their accuracy, and in terms of responsibility for EWS that are not standardized across municipalities.

	2.1.13. What are the capacities to operate climate services?	Gaps were identified in capabilities to map risks, and due to limited coordination. There is no unified database for climate information that could support planning.
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Table 3: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 1.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews and workshop
Co-exploring governance context	2.2.1. What decisions (policy/institutional or individual level) address the risk/adaptation challenges and may benefit from risk information? AND 2.2.2. What institutions have responsibility/mandates for the issues being discussed?	Specific challenges and goals to be addressed are currently being debated – exploration of the associated responsibilities will follow. Municipalities and first responders have already been identified in need of improved collaboration, forecasting, climate risk information, and harmonized EWS. The involvement of police (responsible for event coordination) is currently discussed.
	2.2.4 Are multiple risks being considered, and are there any risks of compound or cascading effects?	Compound flood events have been identified as an opportunity for (Risk)-Tandem, as little information is available. Effects of windstorms to flood risks have also been discussed.
	2.2.5 Are there multiple decision-makers or groups at different scales, for whom different types of information is required?	The primary focus of RWL 1 rests on municipalities – access to national level decision-making is limited. Equally, citizen engagement has been discussed as a challenge (see below).

	2.2.10. Can examples from other cities or contexts help to spur possible adaptation measures?	A webinar series was arranged to promote the exchange of ideas for all RWLs, and a peer-learning sessions between Labs are currently being planned.
	2.2.12./19 Have “windows of opportunity’ been identified in policy development or planning processes where climate information can be integrated?	The creation of the new Ministry for Social Security and Emergency Preparedness may provide opportunities for DIRECTED, but their exact role is not entirely clear. In addition, the expansion of the EU Floods Directive to Roskilde Fjord is likely to increase the number of municipal risk management plans from the current 27 to 51.
	2.2.25 What are the practical constraints to developing risk/climate information services or governance solutions (in terms of time, budget, human or financial capacities)?	Reflected further below.

Table 4: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information needs in RWL 1.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews and workshop
2.3. Co-exploring information needs	2.3.1 Has climate information already been factored into decisions at organizational, individual or policy-making levels?	Yes, to a degree. However, there is no unified standard or coordinated approach for decision-making across municipalities, and debates exist regarding the most appropriate RCPs, for instance.

	<p>2.3.2. What limits the use of risk information?</p>	<p>Capacities, competing databases and lack of nationwide solutions, such as an environmental portal for sources of knowledge. Forecasting issues were highlighted numerous times, partly due to inaccuracies, and due to the limited level of detail for the measurements of wave heights and storm surge risks, for instance.</p>
	<p>2.3.3/7 How can activities be designed to communicate to and engage participants with climate risk assessments, global climate modelling and projections and downscaling of data?</p>	<p>The workshop utilized graphics and a map of the Capital Region to assist in communicating long-term climate projections to stakeholders.</p>
	<p>2.3.4. What existing weather or climate information is available from local providers, including meteorological departments or private companies? What are the issues of access and data sharing?</p>	<p>DTU and the Danish Coastal Authority both maintain information relevant for the DIRECTED purposes. Options for data sharing are currently being explored to support the Data Fabric.</p>
	<p>2.3.5. What is the time horizon and spatial scale of decision-making needs?</p>	<p>Short-term and long-term needs (>2050) have been identified for different purposes – for first responders and for long-term integrated risk reduction.</p>
	<p>2.3.9/10/11 What are the different communication needs/users' perceptions and languages used to describe shared concepts related to risk and climate change? How do these require adapting?</p>	<p>Since the current composition of the Lab involves municipalities (DRR/CCA planners, practitioners, emergency managers), they are broadly at the 'same level'. Specific communication needs are likely to emerge as the Lab continues to engage beyond its current scope.</p>

	<p>2.3.12. Are data available to represent different vulnerabilities and include them in the further analysis?</p>	<p>The Danish Coastal Authority hosts a vulnerability database. Options for its leveraging under DIRECTED are being explored.</p>
	<p>2.3.16. What are the limitations of currently available climate information?</p>	<p>In the Capital Region, different projections and scenarios are used between municipalities. Its integration to DRR planning is inconsistent, and accuracy of flood forecasting tends to vary according to stakeholders.</p>
	<p>2.3.18. In what formats do users prefer or require climate information, e.g. risk maps, probabilistic charts, seasonal time-series, etc.? What about information on uncertainty?</p>	<p>Visualized risk information is appreciated. Information on uncertainty is not currently well-understood or communicated between stakeholders (accuracy is consistently highlighted instead).</p>
	<p>2.3.19. What planning tools or impact models are used, and what are appropriate formats of climate information?</p>	<p>Discussed in detail under 5.1. and 5.2., under user needs and the design of the Data Fabric.</p>
	<p>2.3.20. Are there specific capacity needs to interpret model outputs?</p>	<p>To be further discussed in the context of user training for the Data Fabric. To date, capacity needs regarding GIS mapping for municipalities have been identified.</p>

Reflections on challenges of Tandem implementation in

RWL 1

During scoping consultations and debriefs, several challenges pertaining to co-production have been outlined. These include:

- Turnover of staff, causing minor delays over 2023. This also has an impact on engagement and capacity development, as the delivery of (Risk)-Tandem must be adapted depending on changes.
- Organizational culture, and the set-up of the RWL. Due to limited earlier engagement, the hosts noted that the stakeholders would not appreciate “playing games” or interactive exercises, and the plan to host an event simulation activity in August 2024 was postponed. Although the workshop was a success, there is a pressure to produce results – primarily in the form of technical solutions. The governance context and challenges (such as issues of communication, coordination, and potential ways forward) remain underexplored.
- Although flood/storm risks and associated climate projections are currently discussed in detail, aspects of multi-hazard risk management are yet to be co-explored. Similarly, the degree to which considerations for social vulnerability can be integrated into planning requires further discussions; to date, stakeholders have expressed the need to have information regarding the location of vulnerable populations in the Capital Region. Data availability is currently being explored.
- Stakeholder fatigue is a concern, in terms of competing priorities arising from numerous DIRECTED partners. Research, user needs discussions, workshops and associated planning, and interviews tend to generate a burden for RWL hosts, and risk alienating stakeholders. The Lab participants have agreed to meet in person twice per year.
- Citizen engagement and progress toward “transdisciplinary” Labs is slow, partly due to issues of accountability (municipalities maintaining responsibility over citizen engagement), and due to limited experience in engaging with citizens. Improving risk communication has been highlighted as a potential window of opportunity by the stakeholders.

Ways forward

Theory of Change, MEL, and a roadmap for the RWL are currently being negotiated based on identified needs, priorities, challenges, and potential windows of opportunity. They will be finalized toward the end of Q4 of 2024, to support beginning the co-production of risk governance “solutions” and the Data Fabric. Formal capacity needs assessments (WP 4) and research targeting the risk governance landscape (WP 3) will also be conducted to identify critical needs in terms of enabling transdisciplinary co-production processes, beyond co-exploration.

Table 5: RWL 1 document sources.

<u>Document</u>	<u>Link</u>
Workshop II Report and Summary	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/apps/files/files/587135974?dir=/directed_shared/work_packages/wp1_rwl/RWL%201%20The%20Capital%20Region%20of%20Denmark/2nd%20workshop%20RWL1%2020082024&openfile=true
Workshop II Debrief	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/apps/files/files/587138683?dir=/directed_shared/work_packages/wp1_rwl/RWL%201%20The%20Capital%20Region%20of%20Denmark/2nd%20workshop%20RWL1%2020082024&openfile=true
Interviews with stakeholders (Folder)	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/apps/files/files/537874807?dir=/directed_shared/work_packages/wp1_rwl/RWL%201%20The%20Capital%20Region%20of%20Denmark/Interviews%20with%20stakeholders%20April%20%26%20May%202024
M3 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/HBDiwwBWd35fo42
M4 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/z7EqMNAzAFKA2gH
D5.2. User Stories	Currently, in draft format. https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/YNttTpFkTzMpSc8

1.1.2 RWL 2: Emilia-Romagna Region

During Q1 and Q2 of 2024, the majority of the efforts of RWL 2 were geared toward the General Assembly in Rimini, Italy, and the associated flood risk simulation involving stakeholders across scales (including volunteers and the Civil Protection of Emilia-Romagna). WPs 4, 3 and 5 provided their support to its delivery and design, although hosts of the Lab should be primarily credited for the practical simulation effort itself. This provided an opportunity to test the response mechanisms vis-à-vis a flood scenario affecting the Marecchia and its minor tributaries incorporating extreme climate impacts to precipitation and storm surges in the region, based on Copernicus data (corresponding to a 2050 scenario with 10-year return period).

The event itself was divided into forecasting phases (activation of prevention actions across scales) and the event phase (activation of monitoring, countering and managing the emergency) at regional, provincial, and municipal levels (including volunteers). The intention was to use this simulation as an opportunity to diagnose potential issues in the emergency management mechanism, and Tandem questions were integrated into the evaluation questionnaire distributed to project partners. The exercise was perhaps too well planned as a

demonstration of the impressive capabilities of the civil protection agencies and volunteers, as the evaluation did not become useful in terms of identification of gaps or challenges. It did, however, detail the operational structure of emergency response and event management, which is useful for the purposes of generating an understanding of the risk governance context and division of accountability.

Fortunately, due to the success of the workshops during 2023 in Comacchio and Mesola, and Rimini and Riccione, many of the issues, challenges and priorities have already been outlined (discussed in M3, M4, and further below). Co-production related activities included rich picture mapping and prioritization exercises to identify priorities for integrated flood risk management in the Marecchia coast (now acting as a baseline for setting goals and a theory of change). WPs 4 and 3 have also contributed to the user needs discussions and mapping, seeking to evaluate the information needs for the purposes of the Data Fabric (WP 5) as well.

At the time of writing, planning and scoping activities are currently supporting the design of the Ferrara Workshop in November 2024, dedicated to examining the issues of wildfire risk management and communication. Building upon scoping and identified challenges – partly from WP 4-led interviews seeking to understand gaps between policies and practical needs – relevant Tandem questions and co-production activities are currently being integrated in the agenda (similarly to 2023 workshops). Consultations and tailored support are being provided to hosts, as a part of the capacity development approach. Despite the workshop being delayed to November from the intended date in October (due to flooding affecting the Emilia-Romagna Region during Q3), progress is steady toward Phase III of (Risk)-Tandem implementation. To further support this, Theory of Change for the RWL will be finalized after the third workshop, and capacity needs assessment will be delivered – keeping in mind the context-specific priorities and challenges as discussed here, and in milestones 3 and 4.

Table 6: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 2 context.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews and workshops (partly combining insights from workshops of 2023 that addressed these questions ahead of schedule).

2.1 Co-exploring risk/adaptation challenges	2.1.1 What are the risk and adaptation challenges currently experienced, and what are their drivers (including physical, social, economic, or political dimensions)?	Addressed through interviews and workshops, with a focus on understanding compound flood risks in the coastal areas of Emilia-Romagna, and wildfire risks in Ferrara. Physical vulnerabilities are well-understood in both cases, and economic losses and impacts, are currently being explored via modelling.
	2.1.3. What risk or adaptation challenges expressed by stakeholders could be addressed with better information?	Information regarding the interactions of floods and pluvial rain are required to understand the compound effects of flooding (currently addressed). In regard to wildfires (currently relying on volunteer prediction and risk maps), sources of data are being explored with partners.
	2.1.4. Who is affected by risks and how? What characteristics contribute to their vulnerability and how? AND 2.1.7. What other drivers of change related to social vulnerability and socio-economic development exacerbate challenges?	Discussions regarding socio-economic vulnerability and risk drivers were explored in the workshop of 2023. The potential of adding vulnerability information to modelling services is being explored, and discussions regarding wildfire risk communication/awareness are likely to further deepen the understanding of the intersection of socio-economic context and hazards.
	2.1.5. What are the climate risks, affected sectors, and spatiotemporal scales for addressing risk governance challenges?	The RWL focuses on supporting emergency management and response, as well as long-term integrated risk reduction. In both cases, questions regarding current preparedness measures, land use, and lack of mainstreaming of climate change considerations in risk reduction policies have been discussed. Sectoral impacts have been explored (see report on workshop 2).

	<p>2.1.10/11/12 What are the existing climate services or warning systems that could be used to reduce risks, and how can they be made useful?</p>	<p>For wildfire risks, the Civil Protection issues a warning bulletin seasonally, and maintains a well-organized volunteer network for monitoring during high season. Communication relies on the Tetra radio network that could be expanded, and the bulletin is not well known among the public. Increase of anemometers, and the implementation of fire propagation models to current risk mapping could be useful.</p> <p>For flood risks, the unique alert system is maintained by the Regional Functional Center, Hera service providers, and others. The UUSSA Single Warning System Offices provide information, and there is a network of private hydrometers on main rivers, and tide gauges on the coast (not integrated into institutional networks).</p>
	<p>2.1.13. What are the capacities to operate climate services?</p>	<p>Capacities to operate climate services in RWL 2 are excellent, although they may vary depending on, for instance, the degree of volunteer networks.</p>

Table 7: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 2.

<p>Framework element (2. Co-exploration)</p>	<p>Guidance question</p>	<p>Notes on application through interviews and workshop</p>
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Co-exploring governance context	<p>2.2.1. What decisions (policy/institutional or individual level) address the risk/adaptation challenges and may benefit from risk information?</p> <p>AND 2.2.2. What institutions have responsibility/mandates for the issues being discussed?</p>	<p>Management structures for wildfire and wildfire risks differ – see D1.1 and workshop report 2 for more detail. Risk information in both cases is detailed, including who could benefit from the integration of available knowledges (particularly between public/private operators). The primary mandates for risk reduction and climate change adaptation are held by the civil protection agencies and municipalities.</p>
	<p>2.2.4 Are multiple risks being considered, and are there any risks of compound or cascading effects?</p>	<p>The compound effects of flooding are considered in Comacchio and Mesola, in consideration of the 2023 flooding of Emilia-Romagna. Wildfire risks are also examined from the perspective of risk drivers and sectoral impacts/interactions (tourism and forestry).</p>
	<p>2.2.5 Are there multiple decision-makers or groups at different scales, for whom different types of information is required?</p>	<p>Differences between information needs have been identified, especially in terms of wildfires. The workshop of November 2024 will examine the information needs of citizens and tourists (as well as hoteliers and the private sector) to improve public risk communication and risk awareness.</p>
	<p>2.2.10. Can examples from other cities or contexts help to spur possible adaptation measures?</p>	<p>A webinar series was arranged to promote the exchange of ideas for all RWLs, and a peer-learning sessions between Labs are currently being planned.</p>

	<p>2.2.12./19 Have “windows of opportunity’ been identified in policy development or planning processes where climate information can be integrated?</p>	<p>Opportunities from scoping include; improving risk awareness and public risk communication; strengthening EWS and knowledge management by promoting collaboration with service providers; involving beach owners and hoteliers in risk governance; involving fire brigade in forest management; supporting the mainstreaming of climate considerations into existing planning and modelling; improving communication between municipalities. These are detailed further in M3, M4 and the workshop 2 report.</p>
	<p>2.2.25 What are the practical constraints to developing risk/climate information services or governance solutions (in terms of time, budget, human or financial capacities)?</p>	<p>Limited coordination between private/public service providers. Communication between municipalities is closely linked to the ability to develop local scenarios, and the available information does not necessarily support these. Integration of sensor data is inconsistent, and data sources compete with each other. Municipalities need to access data directly, and a common management system is deemed beneficial. A closer relationship between institutions and sectors involved is missing. Other issues are further detailed in M3/4.</p>

Table 8: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 2 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem).

<p>Framework element (2. Co-exploration)</p>	<p>Guidance question</p>	<p>Notes on application through interviews and workshop</p>

2.3. Co-exploring information needs	2.3.1 Has climate information already been factored into decisions at organizational, individual or policy-making levels?	Not at the policy level, and its integration in different risk management approaches remains inconsistent across sectors. Most organizations and civil protection agencies are well-aware of the need to integrate such data.
	2.3.2. What limits the use of risk information?	Depends on the level – for citizens, lack of risk awareness and limited communication of the wildfire risk bulletin, for instance. For flood risk management, lack of shared risk information systems on hydraulic monitoring.
	2.3.3/7 How can activities be designed to communicate to and engage participants in climate risk assessments, global climate modelling and projections and downscaling of data?	All RWL 2 engagements have leveraged either a modelling component focusing on data visualization or practical exercises, seeking to communicate risk issues in an accessible format. This will continue during upcoming workshops.
	2.3.4. What existing weather or climate information is available from local providers, including meteorological departments or private companies? What are the issues of access and data sharing?	Detailed in the context of user needs, D5.1., D5.2. and the associated documentation. Access and data sharing discussed above.
	2.3.5. What is the time horizon and spatial scale of decision-making needs?	First response, and longer-term risk reduction planning (>2050). To be further explored through the Risk Layering approach.

	<p>2.3.9/10/11 What are the different communication needs/users’ perceptions and languages used to describe shared concepts related to risk and climate change? How do these require adapting?</p>	<p>Discussed above in the context of public risk communication. Further co-exploration needed to ascertain specific stakeholder needs regarding the communication of modelling outputs (for instance, in terms of volunteer networks). It should be noted that technical capacities of stakeholders involved are generally high, but a capacity needs assessment may reveal further gaps.</p>
	<p>2.3.12. Are data available to represent different vulnerabilities and include them in the further analysis?</p>	<p>Currently unavailable beyond economic losses and damages – options for including vulnerability dynamics in further analyses are being explored.</p>
	<p>2.3.16. What are the limitations of currently available climate information?</p>	<p>Uncertainty and scale – the detail to which impacts of climate change can be predicted to support for local planning may not reach the level of granularity as hoped by stakeholders (applies to other RWLs as well). Requires communication regarding uncertainties and expectations, to be addressed further in the context of capacity development.</p>
	<p>2.3.18. In what formats do users prefer or require climate information, e.g. risk maps, probabilistic charts, seasonal time-series, etc.? What about information on uncertainty?</p>	<p>Due to the high technical competency of RWL 2, seasonal time-series, visual risk maps, and probabilistic charts can be made useful – although communication approaches may differ depending on the scales (see discussion above regarding citizens and volunteers).</p>

	<p>2.3.19. What planning tools or impact models are used and what are appropriate formats of climate information?</p>	<p>Detailed further in the context of D2.1, D5.1, D5.2. and the user needs documentation.</p>
	<p>2.3.20. Are there specific capacity needs to interpret model outputs?</p>	<p>Not yet identified.</p>

Reflections on challenges of Tandem implementation in RWL 2

Although RWL 2 has been exceptionally productive in terms of implementing co-production approaches and collaborative activities in their workshops, some challenges remain (discussed during scoping consultations and workshop debrief sessions). These include:

- Competing priorities and stakeholder fatigue. As a high-risk region, stakeholders of Emilia-Romagna face competing priorities (especially during the summer season), and may become overwhelmed when project needs emerge simultaneously. This is currently being managed, but collaboration tends to slow down during the summer period.
- Citizen engagement has been identified as an administrative challenge, as the responsibility and ability for outreach rests on municipalities. They will require a “reason” and support to promote participatory approaches. Risk communication may provide a window of opportunity for addressing this.
- Generally, communication and coordination between municipalities and sectors has been low in the past, but this is currently being addressed by the project. Also, the stakeholders have been developing ad-hoc solutions, such as WhatsApp groups for event coordination, indicating a high interest in developing more formal solutions.
- The need for greater access to resources for volunteers and municipalities, technical monitoring infrastructure, and for the management and maintenance of forested areas (for wildfire risk reduction) has been highlighted. Although these cannot be directly addressed under the project, they can be taken into account during Phase IV targeting up-scaling, policy recommendations and advocacy. These will, however, affect the ability of stakeholders to sustain collaboration in the future.

Ways forward

Theory of Change, MEL, and roadmap for the RWL will be finalized following Ferrara workshop of November 2024, based on identified needs, priorities, challenges, and potential windows of opportunity. Tandem questions and co-exploration ideas for risk communication issues are currently being explored and integrated into the agenda and associated activities, alongside support from modelling partners and WP 3. Formal capacity needs assessments (WP 4) and research targeting the risk governance landscape (WP 3) will also be conducted to identify critical needs in terms of enabling transdisciplinary co-production processes, beyond co-exploration.

Table 9: RWL 2 document sources.

Document	Link
Workshop II Report and Summary	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/apps/files/files/493014940?dir=/directed_shared/work_packages/wp1_rwl/RWL%20%20Emilia%20Romagna/28092023_RWL2_workshop&openfile=true
Rimini Simulation plan	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/apps/files/files/543790732?dir=/directed_shared/meetings/meeting_rimini_june_2024/Simulation&openfile=true
2023 floods post-event analysis (available on Miro)	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPztoHBM=/
M3 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/HBDiwwBWd35fo42
M4 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/z7EqMNAzAFKA2gH
5.2. User stories	Currently, in draft format. https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/YNttTpFkTzMpSc8

1.1.3 RWL 3: The Danube Region

The Danube RWL has progressed during 2024, including via stakeholder interviews and first engagements that sought to kick-start co-exploration of the risk and governance context in Vienna. The sub-lab in the Zala region has emphasized bilateral engagements and scoping of needs due to challenges of the hierarchical risk management landscape, discussed further below. However, progress has been made in terms of identifying opportunities for promoting public/private partnerships in Austria, and for supporting bottom-up risk governance solutions through the Zala Volunteers association and towns involved.

For the September workshop in Vienna, WPs 3, 4 and 5 provided their support to advance a collaborative agenda incorporating demonstration of DIRECTED’s modelling capacities for the Danube region, and a scenario simulation to drive discussion (similar to the Copenhagen workshop in August, 2024) between the public sector, insurance actors, and stakeholders representing academia. The scenario illustrated a 100-year flood that occurred on 17-18 August 2024, shortly before the workshop took place. Furthermore, the workshop entailed a Risk-Tandem exercise to reflect shared DRM/CCA challenges in terms of communication and governance, and to identify barriers related to data availability, forecasting, interoperability, data sharing and uncertainty. Specific gaps and barriers were discussed in the context of the communication chain (for instance, between EFAS, Geosphere, civil protection and Vienna disaster control), and between public and private organizations. The second half of the exercise focused upon visioning, to identify gaps and support integrated risk management and climate change adaptation for public and private sector stakeholders.

Although the integration of Tandem questions and process in terms of knowledge co-production within RWLs has been slower when compared to other Labs, significant progress has been made during 2024 in terms of co-exploration and user needs (under the lead of WP 5). These will be used to discuss and determine a Theory of Change for Vienna and its sub-Lab in Zala, and opportunities for promoting transboundary knowledge exchange will be further explored. At the time of writing, user needs discussions are being arranged with RWL hosts, and further consultations, research for risk governance “baselines”, as well as needs assessments are being scheduled to support Phase III in 2026. In addition, partners from WP 3 will travel to Zala during Q1, 2026, to provide support for planning on the ground.

Table 10: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 3 context.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews, bilateral engagement with stakeholders, and workshop of September 2024
2.1 Co-exploring risk/adaptation challenges	2.1.1 What are the risk and adaptation challenges currently experienced, and what are their drivers (including physical, social, economic, or political dimensions)?	<p>In Vienna, primary hazards relate to flooding of the Danube (compound events in particular, following snowmelt and rainfall). Potential for supporting drought risk management is being explored.</p> <p>For Zala, challenges range from flooding and droughts in the Lake Balaton region to mudslides and wildfires affecting the county. Socio-economic and political dimensions of risk issues require further examination (although the economic loss and damages are well understood in the context of Vienna in particular). However, limited political willingness to support CCA planning has been discussed in the context of Vienna, alongside a lack of connection between DRM/CCA institutions.</p>
	2.1.3. What risk or adaptation challenges expressed by stakeholders could be addressed with better information?	<p>In Vienna, a need for coupled models for fluvial and pluvial flooding has been identified, and existing risk modelling does not include climate change information well enough. The entire Danube region could benefit from a tool capable of disseminating early warnings and “nearcasting” events for disaster response as well.</p> <p>In Zala, any accessible risk information tailored for the County is deemed beneficial, in</p>

		the absence of modelling services and risk maps tailored for sub-national levels.
2.1.4. Who is affected by risks and how? What characteristics contribute to their vulnerability and how?		Issues of vulnerability are not yet examined, beyond economic losses and damages in Vienna.
AND 2.1.7. What other drivers of change related to social vulnerability and socio-economic development exacerbate challenges?		In Zala, areas exposed and vulnerable to multi-hazards are being explored, although the availability of data in small towns across the county is likely an issue.
2.1.5. What are the climate risks, affected sectors, and spatiotemporal scales for addressing risk governance challenges?		RWL 3 maintains a focus on improving response and long-term risk reduction (>100 year events). However, data availability regarding climate change in specific areas is an issue – in the case of Zala), and sectoral impacts require further examination. These are discussed in more detail in M4.
2.1.10/11/12 What are the existing climate services or warning systems that could be used to reduce risks, and how can they be made useful?		Stakeholders from the insurance sector provide numerous private sector services, including the HORA platform enabling users to assess damages vis-à-vis hazard risks. The role of the private sector in disseminating EWS is currently being explored, alongside collaboration between public/private sector actors on the topic.

	<p>2.1.13. What are the capacities to operate climate services?</p>	<p>To be further explored during Q4 of 2024, particularly in the case of Zala where user needs require further discussion.</p>
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Table 11: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 3.

<p>Co-exploring governance context</p>	<p>2.2.1. What decisions (policy/institutional or individual level) address the risk/adaptation challenges and may benefit from risk information?</p> <p>AND 2.2.2. What institutions have responsibility/mandates for the issues being discussed?</p>	<p>In Vienna, private sector and public sector (civil protection) actors have been identified as the primary stakeholders between whom exchange of risk information is deemed beneficial and necessary.</p> <p>In Zala, the volunteer organizations and other local level actors are discussed as the current primary beneficiary for cultivating bottom-up solutions through tailored risk information products. Specific mandates across stakeholders involved require further discussion with the support of WP 3.</p>
	<p>2.2.4 Are multiple risks being considered, and are there any risks of compound or cascading effects?</p>	<p>In Vienna, the compound effects of fluvial and pluvial rain are discussed, alongside the potential to expand the Labs' focus toward droughts.</p> <p>As discussed above, Zala represents an opportunity for discussing multi-hazard risk management, in consideration of climate change impacts. Specific issues across these are yet to be identified.</p>

	<p>2.2.5 Are there multiple decision-makers or groups at different scales, for whom different types of information is required?</p>	<p>In Vienna, the workshop identified specific needs across groups – particularly those affected by risks (as communication channels to the public could be improved). For emergency responders, better information and early warnings are required, whereas planners require more detailed information regarding the projected impacts of climate change.</p> <p>In Zala, volunteer associations and towns require easily accessible and visualized (comprehensive) risk information to support local planning (ideally covering multi-hazard scenarios).</p>
	<p>2.2.10. Can examples from other cities or contexts help to spur possible adaptation measures?</p>	<p>A webinar series was arranged to promote the exchange of ideas for all RWLs, and a peer-learning sessions between Labs are currently being planned.</p>
	<p>2.2.12./19 Have “windows of opportunity’ been identified in policy development or planning processes where climate information can be integrated?</p>	<p>The scoping, Vienna interviews and workshop has contributed to the identification of windows of opportunity, particularly in terms of strengthening the availability of compound flood risk/climate risk information to planners. Collaboration between public/private sector partners is an excellent opportunity for improving coordination and exchange of information (including in terms of EWS). The creation of a DRM/CCA platform has been proposed as an idea, considering the successes of the workshop in 2024. Tools, expansion of the HORA platform, and integrated flood modelling are also identified. In Zala, any risk information products would be beneficial – particularly in the rural regions.</p>

	<p>2.2.25 What are the practical constraints to developing risk/climate information services or governance solutions (in terms of time, budget, human or financial capacities)?</p>	<p>Lack of data and capacity may affect the ability of partners and stakeholders to co-produce risk information products/services in Zala County. Administrative constraints and the RWL context may also create issues for enabling collaboration – these are discussed further below.</p>
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Table 12: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 3 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem).

<p>Framework element (2. Co-exploration)</p>	<p>Guidance question</p>	<p>Notes on application through interviews and workshop</p>
<p>2.3. Co-exploring information needs</p>	<p>2.3.1 Has climate information already been factored into decisions at organizational, individual or policy-making levels?</p>	<p>Workshop summaries discussed the limited use of climate information in current modelling, lack of specificity, and limited engagement between actors working on DRR/CCA.</p> <p>In Zala, data availability for providing tailored predictions for the county remains uncertain, but is currently explored.</p>
	<p>2.3.2. What limits the use of risk information?</p>	<p>Limited collaboration and use of risk management tools (particularly between public/private sectors). Further exchange is needed. In addition, modelling resolution could be improved, and data availability in general tends to be very costly (or limited).</p>

	<p>2.3.3/7 How can activities be designed to communicate to and engage participants to climate risk assessments, global climate modelling and projections and downscaling of data?</p>	<p>Building on the successes of the Copenhagen workshop, Vienna engagements also leveraged a scenario-based exercise with the support of WP 5 partners.</p>
	<p>2.3.4. What existing weather or climate information is available from local providers, including meteorological departments or private companies? What are the issues of access and data sharing?</p>	<p>See above.</p>
	<p>2.3.9/10/11 What are the different communication needs/users perceptions and languages used to describe shared concepts related to risk and climate change? How do these require adapting?</p>	<p>Not yet explored.</p>
	<p>2.3.12. Are data available to represent different vulnerabilities and include them in the further analysis?</p>	<p>Currently not discussed.</p>
	<p>2.3.16. What are the limitations of currently available climate information?</p>	<p>See above.</p>

	<p>2.3.18. In what formats do users prefer or require climate information, e.g. risk maps, probabilistic charts, seasonal time-series, etc.? What about information on uncertainty?</p>	<p>Depending on the level, probabilistic information and technical products are likely preferred. For Zala, volunteers and public risk communication, well-designed and tailored risk maps for the county are preferred as a starting point.</p>
	<p>2.3.19. What planning tools or impact models are used and what are appropriate formats of climate information?</p>	<p>Currently being discussed under the user needs process, D5.1 and D5.2.</p>
	<p>2.3.20. Are there specific capacity needs to interpret model outputs?</p>	<p>To be explored further</p>

Reflections on challenges of Tandem implementation in RWL 3

Given the locally led nature of the project, and high reliance on RWL hosts for enabling collaboration through workshop-based engagements, the process of promoting knowledge co-production is unique in each case. In RWL 3, the implementation of (Risk)-Tandem has been adapted to suit their current timeline, and more resources are being invested to further co-explore challenges and opportunities to premise Phase III. Challenges identified to date include:

- Differing perspectives and priorities between Labs and DIRECTED partners. Given the design of the project, the intention is not to provide top-down solutions and strict pathways on RWL design. Consequently, differing priorities and approaches to implementation emerge, and thus require navigation and discussions regarding trade-offs to meet the project’s goals whilst remaining responsive to local needs.

- Socio-cultural context of implementation. In the case of Austria, the bureaucratic context has been highlighted as an issue that may potentially affect the willingness of stakeholders to partake in “creative” workshops and co-productive modes of working. The issue is more prominent in Zala, characterized by a hierarchical command structure where stakeholders across levels rarely interact in a collaborative manner. Entry points for the project are presently negotiated, and opportunities have been identified at the local level. It is important to note that co-production will take different formats depending on the starting point and buy-in of stakeholders.
- Although most RWLs have a preference toward technological solutions and products, these are magnified in the context of RWL 3 and Zala. To promote considerations for the risk governance context and “soft solutions’ for strengthening integrated governance, more support is required (to grasp existing momentum now that stakeholders have shared positive feedback regarding the first engagement and collaboration in Vienna).

Ways forward

At the time of writing, user stories for both Vienna and Zala are being discussed and finalized to support D5.2. As a part of this process, clear objectives and priorities are being identified, which can also support the establishment of theories of change (based on the workshop outcomes in Vienna). For Zala, partners continue investing more support for kick-starting knowledge co-production, including attending in person to support planning during Q1 of 2025. Bilateral engagements from the past year are being analyzed and discussed to identify potential entry points.

Table 13: RWL 3 document sources.

<u>Document</u>	<u>Link</u>
Workshop I report and summary	Unavailable online at the time of writing
Interview reflections and summary (available on Miro, RWL 3)	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPztoHBM=/
M3 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/HBDiwwBWd35fo42
M4 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/z7EqMNAzAFKA2gH
5.2. User stories	Currently, in draft format. https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/YNttTpFkTzMpSc8

1.1.4 RWL 4: Rhine-Erft

Hosts of RWL 4 have progressed rapidly in enabling knowledge co-production through scoping engagements and workshops designed to co-explore the risk governance context. Since the last reporting period (between November 2023 and October 2024), three workshops and bilateral engagements have been delivered, in consideration of the (Risk)-Tandem application. The third RWL meeting (20 November, 2024), focused on discussions exploring available flood risk information and the Erft warning system, and presentations of the operation challenges in coping with major events. In addition, discussions identified issues in terms of communication, public risk awareness, involvement of municipalities in DIRECTED actions, and finding possible interfaces between operational flood protection, research and practice. A regular DIRECTED newsletter was established to communicate DIRECTED updates to stakeholders.

Tandem guiding questions and co-production methods were used to support the design of the fourth workshop on 18 March 2024, which sought to identify gaps and opportunities in improving communication between RWL stakeholders (municipalities, planners, and actors working with DRR and CCA). Based primarily on interactive exercises, the agenda included an update on RWL progress, introduction to the KRITIS-dialogue project on communication, and detailed clarification of the command procedure in the event of imminent or actual flooding (to be used as a basis for a tabletop exercise in January 2025). This resulted in the creation of a Webex-based flood risk coordination system, from triggering of flood alerts in the North Rhine-Westphalia in HOWIS to situational assessments and meetings to distribute responsibilities and share information. This was tested in May 2024, with positive feedback from all participants.

The fifth workshop (19 August, 2024) was less interactive, providing project updates and a demonstration of DIRECTED's modelling capacities (SaferPlaces), and presentation of the Civil Protection System and volunteer coordination in Emilia-Romagna, emphasizing peer-learning. The Webex coordination system feedback was discussed in detail to further improve its implementation, and to improve the flow of information to municipalities (including a reporting agreement on where, how and when information will be provided, signed by district administrators). Overall, stakeholders are satisfied with the process, although significant efforts are now required from partners to support the delivery of the tabletop exercise in January – designed to explore practical challenges in event management based on a past flood event simulation.

Table 14: Relevant Tandem questions that have been adapted for co-exploration of risk and adaptation challenges in RWL 4 context.

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews, bilateral engagement with stakeholders, and workshops
2.1 Co-exploring risk/adaptation challenges	2.1.1 What are the risk and adaptation challenges currently experienced, and what are their drivers (including physical, social, economic, or political dimensions)?	Currently, RWL 4 emphasizes flood risks in the Rhine-Erft. Iterative co-exploration and scoping of drought risks (and relevant stakeholders) is currently being planned for years 2025-26, to run parallel with integrated flood risk reduction planning. In terms of risk drivers, the cessation of lignite mining in the area is likely to contribute to changing flood risks and the landscape (and may provide windows of opportunity for DIRECTED). These and the policy-related challenges are further discussed under M4.
	2.1.3. What risk or adaptation challenges expressed by stakeholders could be addressed with better information?	These will be further discussed through the tabletop exercise in January 2025. To date, stakeholders have identified the need to improve the flow of information on river/surface water floodings, as well as droughts.
	2.1.4. Who is affected by risks and how? What characteristics contribute to their vulnerability and how? AND 2.1.7. What other drivers of change related to social vulnerability and socio-	Currently, dynamics of vulnerability have not been discussed (although it is generally recognized that the flooding of 2021, for instance, revealed vulnerability dynamics relating to age and difficulties to evacuate). Limited information available on citizen vulnerability.

	<p>economic development exacerbate challenges?</p>	
	<p>2.1.5. What are the climate risks, affected sectors, and spatiotemporal scales for addressing risk governance challenges?</p>	<p>Municipalities, the water boards and administrative districts use flood risk information for their planning. These differ from short term needs for emergency responders and civil protection (primarily interested in situational assessments, EWS and emergency response). Sectoral impacts are yet to be explored in detail.</p>
	<p>2.1.10/11/12 What are the existing climate services or warning systems that could be used to reduce risks, and how can they be made useful?</p>	<p>Currently, hydrological situation reports are generated in the sub-basins for emergency management, alongside a Flood Information System (HOWIS) maintained by Ertverband. Weather forecasts are provided by the DWD. Strengthening existing services are being explored based on workshop outcomes, and as a part of the user stories research. Webex has already been established for coordinating event response information sharing.</p>
	<p>2.1.13. What are the capacities to operate climate services?</p>	<p>High workloads and limited staff tend to affect the assessment of urgent flood situations (sometimes leading to delays in warnings). Technical competencies for systems used by municipalities, water authorities and civil protection staff require further examination vis-à-vis the Data Fabric development. Information is largely sourced from websites and apps – modelling or software are not commonly used. Available information is also difficult to interpret (particularly in terms of uncertainties).</p>

Table 15: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of risk governance context challenges in RWL 4.

Co-exploring governance context	<p>2.2.1. What decisions (policy/institutional or individual level) address the risk/adaptation challenges and may benefit from risk information?</p> <p>AND 2.2.2. What institutions have responsibility/mandates for the issues being discussed?</p>	<p>The pathways for supporting emergency response with improved information flows are well understood (amidst municipalities and emergency responders, including improving the access of fire brigade to risk information). See M4 for more detail. In terms of public risk communication, challenges regarding risk awareness have been highlighted. Mandates are discussed in 4th workshop outcomes (Miro) and M4. These will be further addressed in the upcoming workshops, especially in terms of integrating climate risk information and long-term planning. Currently Erftverband maintains responsibility over the planning of river restoration and flood retention, which may provide opportunities for DIRECTED. However, they are not officially part of the warning and information chain.</p>
	<p>2.2.4 Are multiple risks being considered, and are there any risks of compound or cascading effects?</p>	<p>Focus on multi-hazard risk management is limited, and cascading impacts are not yet addressed. These will be explored further as a part of the tabletop exercise, co-produced between partners and hosts. Drought will be introduced as a theme during 2025 (requiring returning to scoping activities).</p>
	<p>2.2.5 Are there multiple decision-makers or groups at different scales, for whom different types of information is required?</p>	<p>Impact-based forecasts and maps are considered beneficial for municipalities, alongside radar based EWS. For water boards, improved access to water level information has been highlighted, and first responders require data on compound effects. Citizens would</p>

		benefit from knowledge regarding high-risk areas/impacts.
	2.2.10. Can examples from other cities or contexts help to spur possible adaptation measures?	A webinar series was arranged to promote the exchange of ideas for all RWLs, and a peer-learning sessions between Labs are currently being planned.
	2.2.12./19 Have “windows of opportunity’ been identified in policy development or planning processes where climate information can be integrated?	Windows of opportunity include risk communication between municipal/civil protection stakeholders, and identifying a role for the Ertverband amidst these. Flood retention planning, river restoration, and drought risk management are currently being explored, and the tabletop exercise is expected to reveal others.

Table 16: Relevant Tandem questions which have been adapted for co-exploration of information in RWL 4 (note: covered in more detail by WP 5, not only Tandem).

Framework element (2. Co-exploration)	Guidance question	Notes on application through interviews, bilateral engagement with stakeholders, and workshops
2.3. Co-exploring information needs	2.3.1 Has climate information already been factored into decisions at organizational, individual or policy-making levels?	Remains to be further explored. Presently, severe flooding and its impacts are being explored due to its high priority, which also allows the building of relationships within the RWL.

	<p>2.3.2. What limits the use of risk information?</p>	<p>Limited past coordination, competing information sources, and lack of command structure for creating situational assessments during response (prerequisite for warnings). Currently being addressed via the Webex communication plan. Information is largely sourced from websites and apps – modelling or software are not commonly used.</p>
	<p>2.3.3/7 How can activities be designed to communicate to and engage participants to climate risk assessments, global climate modelling and projections and downscaling of data?</p>	<p>Given issues in interpreting data, stakeholders have expressed interest in accessible and integrated software for flood risk modelling that could support analysis and visualization for flood risk management.</p>
	<p>2.3.4. What existing weather or climate information is available from local providers, including meteorological departments or private companies? What are the issues of access and data sharing?</p>	<p>See above. Modelling and software not generally used by municipal stakeholders and administrative districts. Options for further identifying available information and user needs are currently being explored with project partners.</p>
	<p>2.3.9/10/11 What are the different communication needs/users perceptions and languages used to describe shared concepts related to risk and climate change? How do these require adapting?</p>	<p>To be further discussed.</p>

	<p>2.3.12. Are data available to represent different vulnerabilities and include them in the further analysis?</p>	<p>Not yet addressed.</p>
	<p>2.3.16. What are the limitations of currently available climate information?</p>	<p>Limited information available regarding climate change in the Rhine-Erft.</p>
	<p>2.3.18. In what formats do users prefer or require climate information, e.g. risk maps, probabilistic charts, seasonal time-series, etc.? What about information on uncertainty?</p>	<p>Currently, information needs highlight access to information to support flood response and event management. Long-term planning options will be discussed later. For drought risk reduction, information needs remain unclear.</p>
	<p>2.3.19. What planning tools or impact models are used and what are appropriate formats of climate information?</p>	<p>Currently being explored as a part of the user stories discussions, and D5.1/2</p>
	<p>2.3.20. Are there specific capacity needs to interpret model outputs?</p>	<p>As above, the need for accessible and visualized flood risk information is deemed beneficial, in the absence of tailored information products.</p>

Ways forward

Implementation of Tandem in RWL 4 will focus on supporting the design of a tabletop exercise/simulation for the identification of specific challenges in event management between stakeholders, and to support the management of cascading events (not currently considered). Besides these, 2025 will seek to introduce drought risk as an objective for the Lab, and more work remains to be done to identify opportunities for integrating climate change adaptation into existing planning. Erftverband’s role in managing river restoration and flood retention planning may prove opportune in this regard. For citizen engagement, the collaboration between partners and hosts has identified an opportunity to contribute to risk communication and citizen engagement led by the Flood Protection Corporation, which will be further explored. Theory of Change has been established and is currently being finalized, with MEL planning continuing.

Table 17: RWL 4 document sources.

Document	Link
Workshop reports from meetings 3, 4 and 5 available on Miro	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPztoHBM=/
M3 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/HBDiwwBWd35fo42
M4 Knowledge co-production outcomes	https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/z7EqMNAzAFKA2gH
5.2. User stories	Currently, in draft format. https://cloud.tu-braunschweig.de/s/YNttTpFkTzMpSc8

2. Refining Tandem

Progressing toward D4.3 on refining the Tandem framework, WP 4 has developed an approach to coding and analyzing qualitative data emerging from RWL engagements. In alignment with Tasks 4.1 and 4.4, the application will lead to refinement, development and iterative learning of the existing implementation guidance (since existing materials cannot meet all the emerging needs). For this purpose, the following section will discuss the coding methodology and approach to data analysis to identify shared gaps in the implementation of Tandem based on Milestones 3, 4 and feedback discussions, primarily debriefs and scoping. These will be used for the development of further activities and improved implementation guidance – including a set of capacity development modules that are developed based on DIRECTED engagements and needs assessments (D4.1).

2.1 Methodology

The methodology for identifying gaps in application (since Tandem was developed primarily as guidance to address climate change risks) builds upon the MEL approach as outlined in the D1.2., Capacity Development Strategy for DIRECTED. It combines the “good principles” of knowledge co-production by Norström, et al. (2020) with coded Tandem guiding questions (Table 1), in efforts to elaborate, measure, and learn from knowledge co-production in the Directed RWL contexts. Inductive coding will help revise and refine Tandem guiding questions through new information and codes identified in analyzing the practical implementation of Risk-Tandem knowledge co-production process in risk governance contexts. This will contribute to improving and informing capacity development, and aid in the tailoring of Tandem to emerging needs.

The analysis will primarily focus on Phase II of implementation (2024), but will also include some of the early reflections discussed under M3 on challenges faced during the phase of scoping and set up of RWLs. Although not fully “co-productive”, Phase I is central for understanding the difficulties of setting up transdisciplinary stakeholder collaboration across levels of governance.

Table 18: The combination of Tandem guiding questions categorized under sub-code themes, and the “good principles” of co-production, providing a categorization scheme to evaluate successes and challenges of co-production in RWLs.

Tandem Element	MEL Element ¹	Theme	Sub-code	Impact code ²
Scope, review identify and engage	Context-based	Risks, vulnerability and challenges (climate and non-climate)	Natural hazards/disaster risks	Holistic overview of risks and vulnerabilities.
			Climate and disaster risks	
			Non-climate/disaster risks	
			Socio-economic vulnerabilities	
	Impacts		Natural hazards/disasters	Holistic overview of impacts.
			Environmental impacts	
			Climate and disaster impacts	
			Non-climate/disaster impacts	
	Pluralistic	Identified and engaged relevant actors and champions	Stakeholders relating to climate/risk information and data	Increased awareness and understanding of knowledge and stakeholder landscape.
			Stakeholders involved in decision-making process	
			Stakeholders vulnerable/at risk	
			Knowledge systems engaged with	Improved communication (e.g. trust, dialogue, co-production, language).
Methods of engagement used				
Co-explore	Goal-oriented	Co-explore challenges and goals	Socio-economic challenges (e.g. income, education)	Creating shared understanding - consensus building around priorities, where it was absent previously, for example.
			Decision-making challenges (e.g. representation, responsibilities, data)	
			Communication challenges (e.g. language, terminology, channels)	
			Adaptation challenges (e.g. climate, social, economic, political, environmental)	
	Co-explore governance context		Windows of opportunity	Increased understand of governance levers of change.
			Institutional capacity/arrangements	
			Existing plans, policies, and projects	
			Governance mechanism	
			Funding	
			Appropriate format	

¹ Norström et al., 2020.

² Potential results from application, not assessed in this milestone.

		Co-explore information needs	Relevant language	Increased awareness and understanding of challenges, risks, and impacts faced through enhanced understanding of the use and limits of data/models.
			Accessible terminology	
			Capacity to articulate needs	
			Information channel	
			Appropriate scales (relevant to temporal and spatial scales of decision)	
Co-design solutions	Co-explore and identify solutions	Relevant to decision context	Solutions that provide increased resilience to climate and disaster risk.	
		Salience (priority need)		
		Credibility (trusted)		

2.1.1 Coding framework design

The coding framework has been developed through a structured approach that inductively categorizes various aspects of risk governance, knowledge co-production, data and models, hazards, and vulnerability. Key elements of the framework are as follows:

Code Groups and Sub-Groups: The framework is organized into primary code groups and sub-groups that provide a more detailed categorization of related concepts. Each group serves as a filter for comparing content across different areas.

- Primary Codes:** These are the main categories that contain broad themes relevant to the analysis. For instance, the framework includes groups like "Risk Governance," "Knowledge Co-Production," "Data and Models," "Hazards and Climate Change," and "Vulnerability." Each of these groups represents a significant area of focus within the overall framework, used to assess successes, opportunities and challenges for knowledge co-production under these thematic areas.
- Sub-Codes:** Within each primary code, there are sub-codes that provide a more organized approach to coding, making it easier to analyze specific aspects of a broader theme. For example, under "Data and Models," sub-codes include "Data Interoperability" and "Data Governance", to support the identification of specific challenges and how the Tandem process has contributed to identifying these in an inter- or transdisciplinary mode.
- Co-occurrence:** The framework emphasizes the importance of co-occurrence, which allows for the identification of relationships between different codes and how different themes interact with one another. This is particularly useful for analyzing how vulnerabilities relate to specific hazards or how data challenges intersect with governance issues, and how knowledge co-production approaches

have contributed to identifying them. For example, discussions about "vulnerability" may be tagged with relevant hazards (e.g., "Flood," "Drought") to analyze how specific vulnerabilities are addressed in the RWLs, and how they are framed vis-à-vis aims of the (Risk)-Tandem implementation process. are affected by different climate related risks.

Tags for Specificity: Tags are used as un-grouped codes that add a layer of specificity, helping users to find topic-specific information more efficiently. They highlight topics or themes that may not fit into the hierarchical structure of primary and sub-codes. Tags such as "Climate Change" or "Uncertainty" can be applied across different code groups, allowing users to quickly locate relevant discussions or data points related to these themes.

See Figure 2 for further explanation of the relationship between primary codes, sub-codes, co-occurrence and tags. The full codebook is not included in this document, and will be submitted with the Deliverable 4.3. as supplementary material (after the coding has been finalized).

Note: AtlasTI does not allow three layers of sub-codes. Therefore, sub-code such as “planning/policy gap” cannot be categorized under its’ parent code “Policy and Planning”. If there is a need to read these side by side, user must tag both codes under co-occurrence analysis.

Code groups are not higher order codes. Instead, they acts as filters that support comparison of content across two different code groups.

Figure 2: Guide to coding in qualitative coding software (AtlasTi).

2.1.2 Coding framework implementation

Implementing the coding framework, in Atlas.ti software in this case, involves several steps, including coding data segments, creating relationships between codes, and utilizing tags for enhanced analysis. The step-by-step implementation is as follows:

Creating Codes: After importing qualitative data into Atlas.ti, codes are created based on the coding framework. Each group and sub-group from the framework are represented as code. For the DIRECTED project, we have grouped the codes as follows.

Group 1: Risk Governance

- Sub-codes: Decision-making, Communication, Coordination, Policy and Planning.

Group 2: Knowledge Co-production

- Sub-codes: Stakeholder Engagement, Knowledge Integration, Citizen Engagement.

Group 3: Data and Models

- Sub-codes: Data Interoperability, Lack of Data, Uncertainty.

Group 4: Hazards and Climate Change

- Sub-codes: Flood, Drought, Wildfire...

Group 5: Vulnerability

- Sub-codes: Economic Vulnerability, Social Vulnerability and Physical vulnerability

Coding Data Segments by highlighting relevant segments of text in the documents and assigning the appropriate codes. For Example; If the report mentions, "We struggle with communication during floods," we highlight this text and code it with "Communication" and "Flood." This allows categorization of the data without missing key information.

Creating Co-occurrences by linking codes that frequently appear together in the data. For Example: If the "Flood" and "Physical Vulnerability" often appear in the same context, we create a co-occurrence relationship. This is done by selecting both codes and using the co-occurrence tool to visualize their relationship.

Utilizing Tags by applying tags to specific themes or issues that arise in the data for easier retrieval and analysis. For Example: in the discussions about "Climate Change Adaptation," we tag those segments, as this allows us to filter and analyze all data related to climate adaptation strategies across different hazards and vulnerabilities.

3. Results

This section will present the findings from the coding. shared gaps/challenges affecting the Tandem implementation in all RWLs, in the context of co-exploration (Phase II) under Risk-Tandem. Milestones 3 and 4 regarding knowledge co-production outcomes have been coded to date, supported by an analysis of debrief consultations and reflections from RWL hosts that also discuss challenges in enabling knowledge co-production. To support analysis, discussions regarding challenges have been categorized according to the MEL framework as outlined in Table 18, in efforts to identify where Tandem can be refined as a guiding tool.

3.1 Phase of Co-exploration

During 2024, the implementation of (Risk)-Tandem has geared toward supporting co-exploration, seeking to enable the deeper examination of contextual risk issues and risk governance challenges through tailored consultations, capacity development and continuous engagement between RWL hosts and DIRECTED partners. In particular, the phase of co-exploration aspires toward impact by 1) creating shared understanding and a consensus around challenges and priorities; 2) increasing the understanding of governance levers required for change, and; 3) increasing awareness and understanding of challenges, risks and impacts faced through increasing knowledge of the use and limits of data and models.

3.1.1 Co-exploring challenges and goals

As evidenced by section 2., Tandem guidance has been used to promote collaborative discussions, and to create spaces for open and inclusive conversations, which is essential for addressing the complex challenges related to disaster risk management (DRM) and climate change adaptation (CCA). The reports note that workshops have generally contributed to providing a platform for stakeholders to voice their concerns and share their experiences. During these workshops, participants discussed specific governance challenges, particularly the need for improved communication between various levels of government. As highlighted in the reports, "Workshops have outlined opportunities to improve collaboration and coordination between DRM/CCA actors toward improved flood risk management". This

dialogue helps uncover underlying issues that may not have been previously recognized, fostering a deeper understanding of the complexities involved.

In most RWLs, existing governance frameworks are not adequately integrating DRM and CCA efforts, leading to fragmented responses to climate-related risks. In addition, heavy preference for response and short-term planning, alongside the lack of political commitment and national support for mainstreaming of CCA considerations across sectors, affect the ability of stakeholders to promote their uptake. The Tandem questions and guidance (although supporting the examination of the governance context), do not necessarily provide solutions to managing issues arising from policy and planning at higher levels of governance, but may help create entry points, surface opportunities or build the relationships that might address such issues.

Relating to this, discussions also revealed several decision-making challenges that impact stakeholders' ability to implement effective DRM and CCA strategies across all RWLs. It has been noted that decision-making often occurs in silos, with different agencies and organizations working independently rather than collaboratively. This fragmentation results in inconsistent policies and actions, making it difficult to address risks comprehensively. Additionally, stakeholders identified challenges related to the availability and accessibility of relevant data, which hinder informed decision-making. Competing priorities further complicate the decision-making process.

In terms of integrating considerations for social vulnerability and the socio-economic contexts, numerous issues arise. In particular, data regarding vulnerabilities is often not available or commonly used, depending on the region. Although recognizing the importance of social vulnerabilities, significant efforts are required to expand co-exploration toward these dimensions from WPs 3, 4 and 5. These issues also intersect with discussions regarding citizen engagement. Although highlighted in the context of RWL 1, 2 and 4, administrative barriers (responsibility of municipalities) limit the ability of hosts to promote transdisciplinary collaboration beyond institutions of the government. In turn, municipalities have limited experience in engaging citizens, and the coding has revealed a tendency to promote risk awareness and risk communication at the expense of participation. As such, because Tandem is not applied in an “ideal world”, outcomes may fall short as a result of real-world bureaucracy.

In terms of cross-agency communication and collaboration, all Labs have identified gaps between stakeholders, including government agencies, community organizations, and the public. These gaps result in inaccuracies, or a lack of awareness about available resources and information. Language is also part of the issue – the implementation of (Risk)-Tandem relies largely on the ability of hosts to translate its concepts to their RWLs. In addition, stakeholders emphasized the need for materials and messages to be tailored to meet the needs of various demographic groups to ensure that all community members are informed and engaged. The report notes, “Developing effective engagement strategies that resonate with different stakeholders remains a challenge”. Stakeholders expressed a strong need for innovative communication methods that foster participation and collaboration, especially

among marginalized groups who may feel excluded from the decision-making process. For addressing these, Tandem guidance should be further expanded toward unpacking communication challenges across scales (currently addressed).

3.1.2 Tandem and co-exploring governance context

The co-production process has revealed several opportunities for stakeholders to enhance governance and improve resilience. Engaging diverse stakeholders has fostered the creation of collaborative networks in RWLs that are better equipped to address governance challenges. These networks promote knowledge sharing and learning, allowing stakeholders to tackle complex issues together. The joint exploration of challenges has sparked innovative ideas and solutions that may not have surfaced in traditional governance structures – including the Webex system, ideas for collaborative DRR/CCA platforms in Vienna, and the multi-stakeholder plan for addressing wildfire and flood risks in RWL 2. The Data Fabric also represents an innovation in this sense, connecting users and modelers in a co-productive process that is rare for EU initiatives.

The Tandem framework has guided and enabled discussions about the capacity development needs of various stakeholders. By identifying gaps in knowledge, skills, and resources, stakeholders can prioritize training and support initiatives aimed at enhancing their governance capabilities. The process has clarified the roles and responsibilities of different institutions involved in DRR and CCA, which is crucial for fostering accountability and ensuring that stakeholders understand their contributions to governance efforts. Although in process, the engagement of multiple institutions has underscored the necessity of collaboration across sectors and governance levels, as effective risk management demands coordinated efforts among local, regional, and national entities (deemed beneficial in all RWL cases according to stakeholder feedback).

However, official administrative responsibilities have limited the scope of collaboration beyond institutions already involved in risk governance processes (particularly in terms of citizen engagement), and the process of bridging CCA with existing DRM/DRR networks is slower than expected. Many RWLs continue emphasizing emergency response, but progress has been made in terms of setting longer-term risk reduction priorities (RWLs 1 and 2 in particular). In all cases, improved forecasting and accessible risk information has been identified as a priority through stakeholder engagement. Additionally, the process has promoted multi-stakeholder engagement as a key governance mechanism. By involving a diverse array of actors, stakeholders can consider a wide range of perspectives and expertise toward integrated DRR/CCA, leading to more robust solutions. Yet, in DIRECTED RWL contexts, information remains expert-led, and room for expanding perspectives beyond current risk management approaches remains a challenge. To address this, peer-learning sessions between Labs will be arranged, and “Idea Lab Sessions” will be organized as a part of the co-production process.

Organizational culture and country context has also been highlighted as a challenge in most of the Labs. In RWL 1, the simulation exercise was delayed due to the time required to build trusting relationships between stakeholders, and it was noted that participants would not “want to play games”. Similar discussions have been had with hosts of RWLs 3 and 4, where the hierarchical governance contexts limit the ability of hosts to arrange collaborative exercises. In Zala, stakeholders of the sub-Lab at different levels of governance are not accustomed to non-hierarchical and transdisciplinary collaboration, and the expectations are characterized by the need for “science” to inform action (conversely to what the project seeks to achieve in terms of co-production). Addressing perceptions requires further discussion and activities, and the product-oriented working mode has created a pressure for co-production activities to generate something tangible (sometimes overlooking trust, new relationships and incremental change already achieved in ways of working). The MEL will further examine these dynamics through comparison of Real World Labs.

3.1.3 Tandem and co-exploration of information needs

Information needs have been well-addressed through the user stories and user needs assessments informing the design of the Data Fabric, and are tangible objectives for each RWL. No significant challenges have been identified, as the “personas” are clearly bounded and provide a direction for travel. This could serve as an inspiration for addressing the communication and governance related questions of Tandem, as the activities may not necessarily produce tangible outputs without activities focusing on prioritization and setting goals. As such, the process could be revised to support a clearer timeline from co-exploration to goal setting, with accompanying activities that have now been developed as a part of the RWL engagements (visualization and prioritization activities that have been leveraged in RWLs 1, 2 and 3).

Information needs for the public, however, present a challenge. Currently, much of the discussions regarding public risk communication emphasize risk awareness and improving the flow of information to citizens, without limited attention (or involvement) of the public to ascertain what their information needs may be. These will be addressed in the RWL 2 workshop in November, seeking to address and unpack wildfire risk communication. The activities can set an example and provide examples for other Labs through peer-learning.

Ambiguities regarding spatiotemporal scales are also an issue. A majority of the Labs maintain a heavy focus on emergency response and short-term needs, whereas information needs for longer-term planning remain more sparse (partly due to uncertainties associated with data, and limited use of probabilistic information in some cases).

4. Refining Tandem

The coding process revealed elements of interest that were not part of the original Tandem coding framework and areas that had already been identified for further research and improvement (e.g. in Bharwani et al., 2024). Thus, the coding process provided clues regarding potential gaps and areas where the co-production framework could be strengthened. These are summarized as follows:

4.1 Integration of DRR and CCA

We recognize there is a lack of coherence when it comes to the relationship between disaster risk management and climate change adaptation policy, and due to its origin in a climate services context, the Tandem guidance does not entail questions specific to managing disaster risk. Coding of qualitative data continues to cultivate guiding questions for knowledge integration between the fields of DRR, DRM and CCA.

This also relates to the fragmentation of data sources, which not only creates gaps in information but also hinders integrated decision-making processes. For example, the need for an "integrated flood model for understanding coastal and riverine flood risk dynamics" was identified as a priority in the Emilia-Romagna Region, underscoring the necessity for a cohesive approach to DRR and CCA data management.

Additionally, the issue of real-time data during emergencies was raised, with municipalities expressing a desire for "additional local measuring points and stations" to enhance the accuracy of forecasts. This highlights a significant gap in the current monitoring infrastructure, which is crucial for timely and effective responses to climate-related disasters.

4.2 Multi-hazard and legacy risk management approach

The reports highlight the complexities involved in multi-hazard risk management, particularly in the Danube, where various environmental and historical factors intersect. There is a notable gap in understanding how different hazards interact with one another. For example, heavy rainfall can lead to flooding, but when combined with snowmelt, the situation can become much more severe. The report states, “The potential compound effects of heavy precipitation and snowmelt runoff have been identified as a priority challenge that current modelling capacities cannot accurately assess.” This illustrates the inadequacy of existing models in capturing these complex interactions, which can result in being unprepared for extreme events.

Additionally, the report discusses historical land-use practices, such as open-pit lignite mining in the Rhine-Erft Region, which have long-term implications for current risk management. The depletion of the groundwater table due to these practices can exacerbate flood risk. This historical context is crucial as it explains how past decisions can create vulnerabilities that endure over time, affecting the region's resilience to both direct and indirect climate-related hazards.

4.3 Citizen engagement

One of the most pressing issues identified across all RWLs is the lack of citizen involvement in disaster risk management (DRM) processes. Although caused by administrative issues and lack of past engagement by municipalities, the ‘real-world’ realities underpinning application of the framework (e.g., staff turnover leading to a loss of legacy knowledge), require further balancing (including with exercises, ideas or capacity development that could support bridging governments and their local context, in the absence of immediate points of entry for transdisciplinary collaboration).

4.4 Communicating uncertainty

In all Labs, stakeholders have identified a need for “more precise” or accurate forecasting for risk reduction purposes. The capabilities to accommodate, address and communicate uncertainty appears low through the analysis of RWL engagements and consultations with RWLs. For this purpose, the Tandem approach could benefit from activities or an approach to manage uncertainty in decision-making contexts, begin with an “expectations management” approach that is presently not included in the guiding documentation or contain more focus on different types of ‘decision framing’ such as when decisions are ‘good enough’, ‘no regret’, produce ‘lock in’, or are ‘irreversible’. Although ‘scoping’ and ‘co-exploration’ aim toward setting these goals, considerations for uncertainty must be consistently highlighted, as stakeholders must navigate the complexities of data interpretation amidst inherent uncertainties. The need to set temporal scales for planning should also be highlighted at the beginning of the process.

4.5 Data interoperability

A need for improved data interoperability among the various stakeholders involved in disaster risk management and climate adaptation is also emerging. This is crucial for ensuring that stakeholders can seamlessly share and access relevant information. Effective data sharing can enhance informed decision-making and facilitate coordinated responses to disasters, ultimately leading to more effective risk management strategies. E.g. examples of differing warning levels and systems in horizontal and vertical channels of communication or governance that do not interact or have the mandate to do so.

4.6 Capacity development

The necessity for ongoing capacity development has emerged as a vital theme, as a response to workshop planning and emerging needs. At the same time, the desire for “formal” capacity development appears low, due to competing priorities and limited time. For managing these, capacity development will resume in a more structured manner, supported by needs assessments, “idea Labs” and peer-exchange, to promote thinking beyond the status quo. These capacity development modules provide complimentary support for the replication of Tandem in other contexts. It should also be noted that the co-production process contributes to the increase in capacities across the entire consortium, including the modelling team. A

MEL approach for assessing its benefits will be considered as a part of the learning approach (see below). Specific capacities required for co-production have been identified, but are refined and tailored in each RWL context (in consideration of different “starting points” and cultural settings).

4.7 Monitoring, evaluation, and learning

The MEL plan is currently being developed and iteratively revised as a part of the Tandem process within Risk-Tandem. This will cultivate a replicable approach that will form a part of the Tandem process for implementation in other contexts (previously identified as an area for further development (Daniels et al., 2021; Bharwani et al., 2024), as often missing in many climate services development processes).

Adaptive governance emphasizes the need for flexible and responsive governance structures that can adapt to changing circumstances and emerging risks. Within Directed, ‘theories of change’ are currently being co-created and indicators co-designed based on identified challenges and priorities. This focus on adaptive governance reflects an understanding that traditional approaches must evolve to better meet the challenges presented by both climate and disaster risk.

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Partners

